

year	treat	block	sampling	Acar_verm	Agal_albi	Allo_obli	Anth_gran	Aphi_goss	Apio_lani	Apis_mell	Asty_vari	Atta_robu	Bemi_taba	Brac_vulg
Year1	nonBt	B1	38DAP	0	1	4	0	1	0	0	4	0	4	0
Year1	nonBt	B2	38DAP	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	15	35	1	1
Year1	nonBt	B3	38DAP	0	7	0	0	3	0	0	12	0	2	2
Year1	Bt	B1	38DAP	0	0	0	0	1	0	2	3	0	1	2
Year1	Bt	B2	38DAP	0	3	0	0	4	0	0	3	0	2	0
Year1	Bt	B3	38DAP	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	7	0	5	0
Year1	nonBt	B1	66DAP	0	0	1	0	294	0	0	0	0	668	0
Year1	nonBt	B2	66DAP	0	0	0	0	135	0	0	0	0	1436	0
Year1	nonBt	B3	66DAP	0	0	0	0	30	0	0	0	0	417	0
Year1	Bt	B1	66DAP	0	0	0	0	170	0	0	0	0	789	0
Year1	Bt	B2	66DAP	0	0	0	0	186	0	0	3	0	499	1
Year1	Bt	B3	66DAP	0	0	2	0	227	0	0	0	0	752	1
Year1	nonBt	B1	81DAP	0	1	0	0	6	0	0	9	0	3183	0
Year1	nonBt	B2	81DAP	0	0	0	0	39	0	0	6	0	2199	0
Year1	nonBt	B3	81DAP	0	3	6	0	20	0	0	0	0	3737	0
Year1	Bt	B1	81DAP	0	4	2	0	20	0	0	4	0	2705	1
Year1	Bt	B2	81DAP	0	1	0	0	18	0	0	13	0	1659	0
Year1	Bt	B3	81DAP	0	1	0	0	22	0	0	5	0	2257	0
Year1	nonBt	B1	102DAP	0	1	1	3	13	0	0	0	0	1864	0
Year1	nonBt	B2	102DAP	0	3	1	7	31	0	0	0	0	2431	1
Year1	nonBt	B3	102DAP	0	1	0	13	22	0	0	0	1	3692	1
Year1	Bt	B1	102DAP	0	1	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	2731	0
Year1	Bt	B2	102DAP	0	0	0	3	9	0	0	0	0	1229	2
Year1	Bt	B3	102DAP	0	4	0	7	0	0	0	0	0	1491	1
Year1	nonBt	B1	121DAP	0	0	0	17	15	1	0	0	0	604	2
Year1	nonBt	B2	121DAP	0	0	0	6	11	0	0	1	32	1206	0
Year1	nonBt	B3	121DAP	0	0	0	7	2	0	0	0	0	1146	1
Year1	Bt	B1	121DAP	0	3	0	11	15	2	1	1	0	537	3
Year1	Bt	B2	121DAP	0	0	6	19	136	1	0	13	0	1138	1
Year1	Bt	B3	121DAP	0	1	6	7	4	0	0	5	0	399	1
Year1	nonBt	B1	142DAP	0	2	0	9	2	0	0	2	0	188	1
Year1	nonBt	B2	142DAP	0	1	0	20	12	0	0	1	0	159	0

Year1	nonBt	B3	142DAP	0	0	0	11	6	0	0	3	1	154	0
Year1	Bt	B1	142DAP	0	2	1	19	19	0	0	0	0	200	0
Year1	Bt	B2	142DAP	0	27	1	27	13	0	0	18	0	315	2
Year1	Bt	B3	142DAP	0	5	21	8	1	0	0	0	0	226	0
Year1	nonBt	B1	164DAP	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Year1	nonBt	B2	164DAP	0	0	6	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Year1	nonBt	B3	164DAP	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Year1	Bt	B1	164DAP	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Year1	Bt	B2	164DAP	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Year1	Bt	B3	164DAP	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Year2	nonBt	B1	59DAP	0	0	0	1	2	0	0	0	1	2039	4
Year2	nonBt	B2	59DAP	0	0	2	4	6	0	0	0	5	945	2
Year2	nonBt	B3	59DAP	0	0	2	4	30	0	0	0	1	1277	6
Year2	Bt	B1	59DAP	0	1	10	1	8	0	0	0	5	1736	1
Year2	Bt	B2	59DAP	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	6	1562	0
Year2	Bt	B3	59DAP	0	0	1	0	71	0	0	0	5	2073	0
Year2	nonBt	B1	74DAP	0	0	0	9	13	0	0	0	0	2355	0
Year2	nonBt	B2	74DAP	0	0	0	7	49	0	0	0	5	4017	0
Year2	nonBt	B3	74DAP	1	1	1	3	6	0	0	0	0	2449	0
Year2	Bt	B1	74DAP	0	0	0	6	74	0	0	0	0	3327	0
Year2	Bt	B2	74DAP	0	0	1	4	29	0	0	0	0	2031	0
Year2	Bt	B3	74DAP	0	0	0	11	2	0	0	0	0	992	0
Year2	nonBt	B1	87DAP	0	0	3	5	28	0	0	0	0	2179	0
Year2	nonBt	B2	87DAP	0	0	3	9	18	0	0	0	0	2757	0
Year2	nonBt	B3	87DAP	0	0	1	11	14	0	0	0	0	1067	0
Year2	Bt	B1	87DAP	0	0	10	5	58	0	0	0	4	1946	0
Year2	Bt	B2	87DAP	0	0	3	6	19	0	0	0	5	1599	1
Year2	Bt	B3	87DAP	0	0	3	10	8	0	0	0	0	2226	0
Year2	nonBt	B1	100DAP	0	0	4	26	8	0	0	0	0	395	0
Year2	nonBt	B2	100DAP	0	0	2	20	6	0	0	0	1	503	0
Year2	nonBt	B3	100DAP	0	0	2	4	2	0	0	0	1	115	0
Year2	Bt	B1	100DAP	0	0	1	7	11	0	0	0	0	769	0
Year2	Bt	B2	100DAP	0	0	0	21	42	0	0	0	0	1413	0

Year2	Bt	B3	100DAP	0	0	0	19	10	0	0	0	1	576	0
Year2	nonBt	B1	115DAP	0	0	1	8	21	0	0	0	1	380	0
Year2	nonBt	B2	115DAP	0	0	0	11	17	0	0	0	0	223	0
Year2	nonBt	B3	115DAP	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	4	436	0
Year2	Bt	B1	115DAP	0	1	0	11	72	0	0	0	0	434	0
Year2	Bt	B2	115DAP	0	0	0	22	7	0	0	0	1	15	0
Year2	Bt	B3	115DAP	0	0	0	12	39	0	0	0	2	273	0
Year2	nonBt	B1	130DAP	0	0	0	20	6	0	0	0	2	99	1
Year2	nonBt	B2	130DAP	0	0	0	13	5	0	0	0	4	119	0
Year2	nonBt	B3	130DAP	0	0	0	11	2	0	0	0	0	324	0
Year2	Bt	B1	130DAP	0	0	0	5	12	0	0	0	0	146	1
Year2	Bt	B2	130DAP	0	0	0	1	6	0	0	1	1	118	0
Year2	Bt	B3	130DAP	0	1	0	6	4	0	0	0	0	81	1

Cato_gran	Chry_exte	Cicl_sang	Cond_long	Diab_spec	Doru_lute	Dysd_rufi	Empo_krae	Erio_conn	Euch_hero	Euxe_stig	Fran_schu	Geoc_sp	Harm_axyr
1	0	0	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
2	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	2	0
0	0	0	1	1	11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
8	0	0	46	0	0	0	0	38	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	1	0	2	0	0	0
0	0	5	4	1	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0
0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
0	0	2	0	1	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	2	4	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	9	7	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	5	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0
0	0	1	2	1	2	0	0	1	2	1	1	3	0
0	1	0	5	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
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0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
0	0	7	5	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0
0	4	0	9	0	0	0	1	6	0	5	0	0	0
10	5	0	3	0	0	0	2	7	0	2	1	0	0
1	1	0	7	0	0	0	0	7	3	1	0	0	0
5	0	0	2	1	0	0	2	4	0	1	0	1	0
0	1	0	10	0	0	0	0	15	0	0	3	0	0
14	4	0	5	0	3	3	3	6	0	1	0	0	0
0	3	0	3	0	0	0	0	15	0	1	0	0	0
0	7	0	1	1	0	0	0	8	0	0	2	0	0
2	8	0	0	1	1	0	0	6	0	1	0	0	0
1	3	1	6	0	0	0	4	34	0	1	0	0	0
0	2	0	2	1	0	0	7	30	0	1	1	0	0
0	3	0	3	0	0	0	0	13	0	0	0	0	0
0	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	9	0	1	0	0	0
0	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	19	0	0	0	0	0

0	5	0	0	0	0	0	12	0	1	0	0	0	0
0	8	0	0	0	0	2	48	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	15	0	0	0	0	0	50	1	0	0	0	0	0
0	7	0	0	0	0	7	50	0	0	0	0	0	0
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0	1	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	1	0	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	3	0	0	0	0	0	2	2	0	0	3	0	0
0	4	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0	2	0	1	0
0	1	5	2	0	0	0	0	1	0	4	1	0	0
0	2	1	1	0	0	0	1	2	1	2	0	0	0
0	3	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
0	2	4	0	1	1	0	2	1	0	3	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	2	2	0	0
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0	3	1	1	0	0	3	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
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0	2	0	1	1	0	11	4	0	0	5	0	0	0
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0	0	1	2	1	0	0	2	3	0	2	0	0	0
0	3	1	1	1	0	0	2	0	1	1	0	0	0
0	1	0	0	0	0	2	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
0	3	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
0	4	0	1	0	0	3	4	1	2	1	0	0	0
0	6	0	1	0	0	2	4	0	0	1	0	0	0
0	2	0	1	0	0	0	2	0	1	2	0	0	0

0	8	7	2	0	0	1	7	1	0	0	0	0	0
0	3	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0
0	6	0	0	0	0	2	3	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	2	0	0	0	0	27	3	0	0	0	0	0	0
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0	2	0	0	0	0	0	7	0	0	2	0	0	0
0	13	0	0	0	0	3	4	0	0	0	1	0	0
0	9	0	0	0	0	5	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	5	0	0	0	0	3	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	9	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	2	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	14	0	0	0	0	12	3	0	0	1	0	0	0

0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	3	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0
0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
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0	3	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
0	7	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0
0	6	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
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0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0
0	2	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0
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0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
0	1	0	0	0	1	2	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	3	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	2	1	0	0	0	0	1	0
0	2	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0

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0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
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0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
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0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
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0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0